

Pushing with a group of mobile robots

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Abstract—This work addresses the problem of manipulating an object on a plane using a group of robots in a collaborative way, applying only pushing actions. The proposed method exploits well known control methods from the robotic literature in designing a multi-layered control algorithm to steer the group of robots in the planar environment to perform a pushing action. The proposed approach is extensively validated by means of simulations and real world experiments involving different objects and robot groups with different numerosity.

Index Terms—Multi-robot systems, Manipulation, Pushing

I. INTRODUCTION & PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

Collaborative transportation of a payload is a very crucial problem among the multi-robot systems literature. Multiple different methods have been identified in literature, however, most notable examples consider the scenarios where the payload is attached to each robot transporting it or the manipulated object, or *manipulandum*, is under force or form closure. In many cases, this type of manipulation can be impossible to perform, either because the object is too large or too delicate to be grasped properly. Non-prehensile manipulation techniques can come in handy in these scenarios.

This work approaches the problem of manipulating an object on a plane, using only pushing actions by a group of mobile robots. In particular, we focus on the problem of controlling the motion of the robots in order to perform such actions. Ideally, the robots should be able to perform a coordinated pushing action moving the object in the direction of the desired object position. In order to solve this problem we propose a control architecture designed to steer the group of robots on the plane. The control architecture is composed by three layers: a position controller higher layer for the regulation of the position of the object, an artificial potential middle layer for the steering of the group of robots around the plane, and a lower layer for coordinated control of the robots. The proposed control architecture has been extensively tested both in simulation and in real world experiments. Furthermore, results are compared with methods from recent literature, showing that the proposed architecture provides a notable increase in performance, regarding the time required to perform a manipulation.

II. PROPOSED APPROACH

The solution we present to the aforementioned problem consists in a control algorithm that coordinates the motion of

the robots on the plane, around the object. The foundational idea of the algorithm is that it is possible to control the displacement of a group of robots to resemble a probability function. This probability density function can then be properly steered around the plane in order to push the target object into the desired position. The lower layer of the control algorithm is responsible to control the displacement of the robots according to the desired probability density function. A common way to achieve this behaviour is through *coverage control* [1]. The shape of the probability density function is defined as a 2D gaussian distribution function. The parameters of this distribution are computed taking into account the footprint of the object to be manipulated and the number of robots.

The task of determining how the distribution has to move across the plane is assigned to the middle layer of the control algorithm. Given a desired motion direction v_{des} for the object, generated by the higher layer for position control, an artificial potential function has been designed taking into account the following required behaviours.

- When too far away from the object, the robots should direct towards the object.
- The robots should avoid contact with the object that would result in pushing opposite to the desired direction.
- The robots should position correctly with respect to the object before pushing.
- The robots pushing action should aim at converging into the desired direction.

The resulting potential function is therefore composed by four action zones, visualized in Figure 1. In Zone 1, depicted in red, a repulsive potential steers the distribution away from the object. When the robots are in Zone 2 (blue), they are pulled towards the object by an attractive potential. The potential in Zone 4 (purple) steers the robots into the object in order for them to properly approach the object before applying the pushing action. In Zone 3, the potential directs the robots around the object till they reach a suitable position for initiating the pushing action. A visualization of the cumulative input of the potential function is provided in Figure 2. The parameters $d_{att}, d_{rep}, \gamma_{lim}$, defining the shape of the 4 zones, are determined once again by the object's footprint. The higher layer for position control is responsible of the generation of the desired motion direction for the object. Many different

strategies could be employed to achieve this task. In this scenario, where there are no obstacles on the plane, the most straightforward way to determine v_{des} is to simply have it directed towards the object's desired position. The attached video shows results of simulations and experiments.

Fig. 1. Action zones of the proposed artificial potential field. The repulsive field acts in Zone 1, shown as the red area. The attractive potential is active in Zone 2, depicted in blue. The yellow annulus sector represents Zone 3 and Zone 4 is represented in purple.

Fig. 2. Artificial potential based cumulative swarm input, oriented accordingly to v_{des} , represented in red.

III. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

The proposed control algorithm has been tested in the CoppeliaSim physical simulation environment. The robot used to validate the algorithm is the e-Puck differential drive mobile robot. The validity of the algorithm has been tested with object shapes and with a different number of robots. The proposed control algorithm has been implemented in MATLAB

language and the resulting commands are transmitted to the robots through ROS communication channels. The validation task for the robot is to carry the object through a series of target positions. On average, the simulated robots were able to perform the given manipulation task in 900s. Similar task was performed also by real robots inside an experiment area. The team of 5 robots performed the manipulation sequence shown in Figure 3 on a square object with an average time of $902 \pm 17s$.

The results of the proposed approach has been also compared with the algorithm designed by the authors of [2], showing that the proposed algorithm can reduce the time required to manipulate an object in half.

Fig. 3. Visualization of the trajectory of the manipulated object (light blue) with the square shape, during the real world experiment, together with the pushing robots (dark blue). The trajectory of the center of mass of the manipulated object is depicted in orange.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The presented work deals with the problem of manipulating an object with a group of mobile robots using only pushing actions. The proposed approach steers the group of robots around the plane as if they were described as a single probability density function and allows to perform an efficient planar manipulation of the object on the plane. The proposed algorithm has been extensively tested in both simulated and real environments, proving an increase in performance with respect to a similar method from literature.

Future work will aim at extending the proposed method towards more general scenarios, including both static and dynamic obstacles in the environment.

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